

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

Deliverable Report

WP4 – Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication

Deliverable D4.5

Leaflets explaining outcomes in lay terms

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Description:

Training material for PAB members to enable their informed participation in decisions on indicator selection and interpreting outcome findings

Publishable summary (max ½ page)

The attached pamphlet is a training tool developed by the STRONG AYA Patient Advisory Board (PAB members) to inform their understanding of the STRONG AYA project and its outcomes for the duration of the project. As co-creation is an integral part of the project's ethos, the PAB was involved, alongside the work package leads, in the creation of their training pamphlets. These pamphlets can serve a dual use in educating various stakeholders on the project in general.

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2 Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)

- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
- **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
- **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
- **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
- **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
- **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

3 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
HCP	Health Care Provider
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
COS	Core Outcome Set
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency

4 Introduction

4.1 Project background

Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age is rare, although 4-6 times more frequent than paediatric cancer (i.e. prepubescent period). However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality-of-life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. Infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

Defining AYAs with cancer as 15 to 39 years at initial cancer diagnosis², their annual cancer incidence is 42.2/100.000, with 156.431 cases in Europe and 1.231.007 cases worldwide reported in 2018 (together 6.8% of all cancers)³. Population-based data from 27 European countries supports that AYAs have lower survival than children but higher than adults affected by cancer. Advances in cancer treatment have led to increased survival rates for AYAs with cancer, improving by 82% for all cancers between 1990 and 2007⁴.

However, survival improvement in AYA is more challenging than for children and older cancer survivors, which might be due to the fact that AYA have the highest absolute excess risk of second primary malignant neoplasms⁵. AYA face some distinct challenges given that they do not belong to neither paediatric nor adult oncology groups. Characteristic features of this population group include unique spectrum of cancer types, different tumour biology, unique complex psychological needs, distinct late sequelae, including impaired fertility, and palliative care. These traits imply that clinical management, treatment, diagnosis, psychological support will need to be designed and developed for AYA's specific needs. For example, AYAs diagnosed with breast and prostate carcinomas have worse survival than older patients because of the biological differences between them, highlighting the need to target screening methodologies, treatment and policies to their needs⁶. AYAs with cancer also face significant psychological challenges, including substance abuse, mental health issues, suicidal ideations and increased emotional burden from cancer and cancer-related morbidity. Finally, tailoring cancer care to AYA's needs is difficult and due to many different complex factors including the low rate of participation by AYAs in clinical trials and cancer research⁷.

Despite the increasing awareness and a growing body of the scientific literature, these unique issues remain to be fully recognised and addressed by the European health systems and AYAs with cancer are frequently underserved. In part, this may have resulted from the traditional dichotomy between the integrated paediatric ("patient/family-centred") care services versus dispersed ("disease- centered") adult oncology

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. *Cancer* 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

² Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology Review Group. Closing the gap: Research and Care Imperatives for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer. National Institute of Health, National Cancer Institute, and Livestrong Young Adult Alliance: Bethesda, MD, USA, 2006.

³ Trama A, Botta L, Steliarova-Foucher E. Cancer Burden in Adolescents and Young Adults: A Review of Epidemiological Evidence. *Cancer J* 2018; 24: 256-266

⁴ Trama A, Botta L, Foschi R et al. Survival of European adolescents and young adults diagnosed with cancer in 2000-07: population-based data from EUROCARE-5. *Lancet Oncol* 2016; 17: 896-906.

⁵ Keegan THM, Bleyer A, Rosenberg AS et al. Second Primary Malignant Neoplasms and Survival in Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors. *JAMA Oncol* 2017; 3: 1554-1557.

⁶ Stark D, Bielack S, Brugieres L et al. Teenagers and young adults with cancer in Europe: from national programmes to a European integrated coordinated project. *European Journal of Cancer Care*, 25(3), 419-427.

⁷ Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

services^{8,9,10}. Up to half of AYAs with cancer report unmet informational and service needs, impacting their direct (survival rates) and indirect (long term effects and mental health) recovery to participate in society¹¹.

Furthermore, aligned with this barrier is the low rate of health care utilisation by AYAs, especially primary care, given their challenges to sustain health insurance coverage¹². According to a survey conducted through the networks of the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOP Europe), 67% of practitioners do not have access to specialised centres for AYA with cancer, 67% had no access to a specialist cancer service for late effects management and 38% had no access to fertility specialists. Under-provision and inequality of AYA cancer care is common across Europe and especially in the Eastern and Southern-East. Furthermore, the Working Group also reported an absence of outcome measures for monitoring and evaluating AYA cancer care programs and control¹³.

Among the recommended future steps, it has been identified that one of the most important contributions to AYA research would be to pool data (e.g. patient-reported outcomes, clinical and treatment data) across institutions and countries and create large cohorts for researchers to Address the burden of cancer in AYA¹⁴. There is a lack of data standardization, data interoperability and (prospective) collection of outcomes of relevance for AYAs with cancer.

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA's experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group.

To this aim, STRONG-AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) and composed of academic research organisations (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), University of Southampton, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, Maastricht University, Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)), clinical partners (Italian National Tumour Institute, Léon Bérard Centre, Gustave Roussy Institute, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, the Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust), stakeholder and patient organisations (Youth Cancer Europe, European Cancer Organisation) and a consulting company (FFUND).

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA data ecosystem will be set up for value-based care, research and policy for AYA with cancer by:

- 1. Developing a Core Outcome Set (COS) specifically for AYAs with cancer, via a participative consensus process defining most important aspects for those directly affected by AYA cancer, including patients and healthcare professionals.**

⁸ Ferrari A, Stark D, Peccatori FA et al. Adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer: a position paper from the AYA Working Group of the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and the European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE). *ESMO Open* 2021; 6: 100096.

⁹ Osborn M, Johnson R, Thompson K et al. Models of care for adolescent and young adult cancer programs. *Pediatr Blood Cancer* 2019; 66: e27991.

¹⁰ Fardell JE, Patterson P, Wakefield CE et al. A Narrative Review of Models of Care for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer: Barriers and Recommendations. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol* 2018; 7: 148-152.

¹¹ Keegan TH, Lichtensztajn DY, Kato I et al. Unmet adolescent and young adult cancer survivors information and service needs: a population-based cancer registry study. *J Cancer Surviv* 2012; 6: 239-250.

¹² Hayashi RJ. Adolescent and young adult cancer survivorship: The new frontier for investigation. *Cancer* 2019; 125: 1976-1978.

¹³ Saloustros E, Stark D, Michailidou K et al. Report on ESMO/SIOPE European Landscape project key results: Mapping the status and needs in AYA cancer care. *Late-breaking and deferred publication abstracts public health* 2017; 28, 5: V643.

¹⁴ Smith AW, Seibel NL, Lewis DR et al. Next steps for adolescent and young adult oncology workshop: An update on progress and recommendations for the future. *Cancer* 2016; 122: 988-999.

2. **Implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems.** Data will be collected at local level and will then be included in a data integration platform. An overall ecosystem framework for data analytics and output will be created supporting federated analyses and the creation of reports across clinical and patient-reported data and making national repositories of (patient-reported) health data, available to individual patients, patient organisations, regulatory authorities, as well as the patients' health care providers to inform clinical decision-making. The five resulting **national ecosystems** will be connected to each other into **the pan-European ecosystem** using a federated approach also utilizing the overall ecosystem framework.

3. **Disseminating the COS to a wide range of local as well as pan-European stakeholders,** in particular by developing analytical tools to process and present patient outcome data and establish feedback loops that inform patients and clinicians.

Implementing these project objectives are five work packages within the STRONG-AYA project:

- WP1: Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer and Data Collection (Lead: SOUTHAMPTON)
- WP2: Governance, Data Security and Ethics (Lead: EORTC)
- WP3: Infrastructure and Interoperability (Lead: UNIMAAS)
- WP4: Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystems, Stakeholder and Patient involvement, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (Lead: E.C.O.)
- WP5: Scientific Coordination and Project Management (Lead: NKI)

STRONG-AYA will enable AYA care and research to benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, the project will leverage the network of interested organisations and networks established under STRONG-AYA for long-term strengthened promotion of the necessary implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe. This will ultimately bring novel insights into AYA cancer care, research and policy, contributing to the long-term improvement of outcomes for people with AYA cancer.

4.2 Deliverable introduction

The Patient Advisory Board, plays an integral role in the STRONG AYA project by providing patient voices, feedback and co-creation involvement to ensure that the project meets the needs of the very people it intends to serve. The purposes of the attached pamphlet is to provide a comprehensive overview of the project in lay language to support the PAB's understanding of the project and its outcomes over the course of the project, whilst also serving as a possible resource to provide the public as well.

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A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for adolescents and young adults (AYA) with cancer

What is Strong-AYA?

Strong-AYA is a European project focused on young people with a lived cancer experience. It involved several organisations that work on specific tasks grouped around important topics such as research, communication, or dissemination. These groups of tasks are called Work Packages (WPs). All 5 of them are explained further.

Work Package 1: Development of the Core Outcome Set

WP1: The main goal of this work package is to figure out the most important things to measure for adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer. This includes things like how the patients themselves report their experiences, as well as their clinical information and treatment details. We want to get agreement on what matters most in understanding and treating cancer in this age group/life stage.

Review of the literature

Interviews with patients

Consensus with experts

Work Package 2: Governance, data privacy, and ethics

WP2: The Strong-AYA project uses sensitive information from young people balancing so we need to balance benefits against privacy and safety risks by following strict ethical and legal principles. WP2 focuses on creating these ethical guidelines. First, risks to privacy and ethics will be identified, then solutions proposed, and assessments conducted. WP2 will create a code of conduct, data agreements, and have independent reviews to ensure ethical compliance throughout the project.

Work Package 3: Infrastructure and Interoperability

WP3: The aim is to develop a data infrastructure and an interaction platform for adolescent and young adult (AYA) cancer care. This will greatly benefit all research with AYAs.

WP3: Infrastructure and Interoperability cont.

For the **STRONG-AYA** project, WP3 will implement its 3 main pillars:

The project respects the data collection practices of its partners and ensures **DATA PRIVACY** in a **SECURE** way.

Data analysis will be conducted using open-source software, **developed and maintained by IKNL**.

FAIR Data Collection

Frequently, gathered data becomes inaccessible, overlooked, or challenging for other researchers and stakeholders to locate. This results in inefficient resource utilization, with multiple research projects redundantly collecting the same data.

Strong-AYA and its partners will thus ensure that gathered data will be:

The goal is to provide evidence-based healthcare for AYAs with cancer. The project strives for open and fair software and services for data analysis.

Re-use of the data will greatly benefit AYAs. Collected and analysed clinical data and patient reported outcomes will help to improve cancer care and treatment at the **policy, organisational, service and interpersonal** level.

Work Package 4: Operation of Strong-AYA ecosystems

WP4: The tasks of WP4 include creating structures to involve relevant stakeholders, ensuring the sustainability and growth of the project by involving patients and stakeholders, and operating and coordinating the Strong-AYA network.

What are the objectives of WP4?

The objectives of WP4 include establishing and supporting national and EU-wide Strong-AYA ecosystems, managing patient data securely, promoting the sustainability and adoption of Strong-AYA throughout and beyond the project, and involving patients and other stakeholders in the project.

To achieve these objectives, WP4 will involve a stakeholder board to ensure their involvement throughout the project, as well as establish a Patient Advisory Board to ensure patient involvement and feedback, raise awareness of the project through meetings and informative webinars, and produce leaflets to help spread the word about Strong-AYA.

Work Package 5: Scientific coordination and project management

WP5: oversees the project strategically and scientifically, managing communication and ensuring effective project management. It uses scientific expertise and teamwork to lead and coordinate the project, setting key goals and monitoring progress. It establishes performance indicators, tracks progress, and shares findings regularly. Additionally, it concentrates on communication strategies to disseminate information effectively network.

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Adolescents and young adults (AYA) who are diagnosed with cancer face unique challenges because they're at a crucial stage of development. Even though cancer in this age group is not as common compared to other ages, it has a big impact on the lives and society. Young people with cancer may lose a lot of their life potential, struggle to work or have a good quality of life, and even face long-lasting health problems during a critical time in their lives.

Most healthcare systems usually treat cancer either as a children's issue or an adult one, which doesn't fully meet the needs of AYAs. Recognizing this gap, the STRONG-AYA Initiative was created to improve the future AYA.

Overarching AIMS

- Create a list of important outcomes specifically for AYAs with cancer, decided through input from those affected, using a shared agreement process.
- Apply this list of outcomes across the European healthcare systems by setting up local units to manage data
- Share this list by creating analytical tools that will allow patients and doctors to learn from their information

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

- The Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI)
- Maastricht University
- Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)
- FFUND BV
- European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC)
- European Cancer Organisation (E.C.O.)
- Youth Cancer Europe
- University of Southampton
- University of Leeds and Leeds Teaching Hospital NHS Trust
- University of Manchester and Christie NHS Foundation Trust
- Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori
- Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard
- Institut Gustave Roussy
- Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie